

**Constructing and Portraying Being 'Genderless' (젠더리스):
A Case Study within the K-Pop Group XLOV**

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Abstract

Rejecting traditional gender expectations and stereotypes have become increasingly visible in popular media. The K-pop group XLOV is the first group with a core concept of 'genderlessness'. This thesis utilized gender theories, primarily from Butler (1999), to explore how XLOV constructs and portrays the concept of genderlessness in a dominantly gender-binary society. As gender studies are lacking in research around gender non-conforming identities, this thesis aimed to bridge this gap in research and bring insight into how gender non-conforming identities are portrayed in popular media. The analysis focused on three music videos and utilized multimodal discourse analysis across lyrical content, choreography, and visual elements in the music videos. XLOV argues that their concept is about rejecting stereotypes and being able to freely express themselves without having to conform to binary expectations. Contrary to the belief that the portrayal of genderlessness involves the absence of gender, XLOV portrays their concept through clearly gendered elements that are blended together to create a hybridity. This hybridity makes it difficult for audiences to assign gender to XLOV's members. The findings indicate that the portrayal of gender non-conforming identities can involve traditionally feminine or masculine gendered elements, but are utilized in a way that does not create sustained gendered performance.

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1. Introduction

The massive uptake in interest in Korean media, specifically popular music and TV dramas, is a global phenomenon that began in the mid-1990s and mid-2000s. Known as the Korean Wave, or Hallyu, the expansion of the fan base to include primarily young people from around the world has led the Korean popular music, or K-pop, industry to become one of the most rapidly growing industries in the world (Korean Cultural Centre, 2017). Research on Korean idols and K-pop groups has increased as the K-pop industry has become more popular among Western audiences. This research includes examining K-pop's influence on identity, fandom spaces, and representation within the industry (Huber, 2023). As K-pop has become a global cultural product consumed by audiences across the world, all in different cultural contexts, this industry has become an area of representation for various identities, including gender. A group that stands out is the four-member idol group XLOV (엑스러브). In only their second year of being an idol group, XLOV has achieved notable visibility in industry chart placements and recognition. They debuted at #2 with their song *I'mma Be* on Genius Korea's daily K-R&B chart (Genius Korea, 2025) and had multiple of their songs place in the top 100 of Genius Korea's *End of Year Charts 2025*: XLOV's title track songs *1&Only* and *Rizz* placed #20 and #78 in the *Top Songs / K-pop* category, and *I'mma Be* placed #19 on *Top Songs / K-R&B* category (Genius Korea, 2026).

Along with XLOV's success within the first year of their career, XLOV presents an interesting case as the first K-pop group with the concept of being a 'genderless' group (KTimes, 2025). The group aligns themselves with the message that gender-specific roles are irrelevant and they reject stereotypical and traditional gender expectations. As rigid and conservative gender stereotypes are dominant in South Korea (Mo & You, 2025), XLOV presents a rare example of rejecting the prevailing gender ideals and expectations in mainstream media and in the K-pop industry. While the K-pop industry has a history of experimenting with gender presentations that blur masculine and feminine elements, these experimentations remain rooted in separated and recognizable binary gender categories. XLOV's concept of a 'genderless' group positions them as beyond these binary gender categories. Against this binary society background, this thesis investigates how XLOV articulate and perform their concept of a 'genderless' identity and aims to answer the following question:

How does K-pop group XLOV construct and portray the concept of 'genderlessness' in their title track songs '*I'mma Be*', '*1&Only*', and '*Rizz*'?

Whilst research on K-pop idols has increased, due to XLOV being early into their career, there is limited research on this specific K-pop group despite their growing popularity. Research on XLOV and how they construct and portray the concept of genderlessness allows for an analysis of an expression of gender that is relatively new in both Korean and Western mainstream media. Due to the newness of discourse around the concept of genderlessness in gender studies, there is a research gap on how this concept is constructed and visible in popular culture, as gender studies thus far have mostly focused on gender within binary understandings, with the exception of a few scholars such as Judith Butler and Anne Fausto-Sterling. This gap has led to studies on gender expressions and identities outside of the male-female gender binary to be neglected. Furthermore, while current research has examined how presentations of masculinity and femininity, and even androgyny are present in popular media (PubAdmin Institute, 2025), there is little attention paid to how concepts such as 'genderlessness' are constructed, communicated, and performed for an audience. Through using XLOV as a case study, this thesis contributes to the limited research on gender performances that do not conform to societal binary expectations of gender. This thesis also contributes to studies

on how gender identities outside of the binary are performed through various means, such as lyrics, dance, dress stylization, and other visual elements, and how these elements combined construct different expressions of gender. By analyzing XLOV and how they present their concept across different forms of media, this thesis contributes to broader discussions on whether mainstream media content can move beyond binary understandings of gender, and incorporate and represent gender non-conforming identities in popular culture.

Furthermore, XLOV has offered their audience a fandom space that has allowed LGBTQ+ fans to feel represented in the K-pop industry, with XLOV's message on gender identity resonating with many fans who felt constrained by binary social norms (S, 2026). Examining the group's presentation of 'genderlessness' is relevant to broader discussions of representation and inclusivity in popular culture. Hence, knowing that XLOV has a massive influence and increasing popularity, this thesis contributes to both academic gaps in gender studies and studies on XLOV as a group, as well as presents the societal relevance of better understanding XLOV and their core message, as they've created a sort of 'safe space' for individuals who search for freedom of expression and representation in media.

This thesis begins by first laying down already existing gender theories to construct a framework on understandings of gender, primarily using concepts from West and Zimmerman (1987) and Butler (1999). Understandings of femininity and masculinity in various settings, such as fashion and dance, are then developed to be able to recognize gendered symbols and roles in the data. Understandings of gender in Korean culture are also discussed to give insight into traditional cultural expectations. Following this, the methodology section introduces XLOV, the aim and relevance of this research, and presents the data used in the case study, the three title track songs, and how this data was collected. The case study section divides the analysis into four different analysis sections and builds on theoretical concepts. The first section analyzes XLOV's own understanding of the concept 'genderlessness', aiming to answer the first part of the research question on how XLOV constructs the concept. This is followed by three analyses for the three different XLOV songs to answer the second part of the research question on how 'genderlessness' is portrayed. This consists of analysis of lyrical content, dance choreography, and elements present in the songs' music videos. The thesis ends by discussing the findings and highlighting key similarities and differences in the three title track songs.

2. Theoretical framework and concepts

2.1 Gender and Identity

The concept of genderlessness challenges traditional binary understandings of gender. To be able to understand genderlessness, gender in this binary tradition is first defined. Firstly, a distinction must be made between sex, which refers to biological characteristics, and gender, which is an achieved status that is constructed through environment (West & Zimmerman, 1987). This distinction between sex and gender is important, as gender is often misunderstood as the same concept as sex. The binary system assumes gender mirrors sex or gender is restricted by sex, however gender is neither the result of sex nor limited by it (Butler, 1999). Gender intersects “with racial, class, ethnic, sexual, and regional modalities” (Butler, 1999, p. 6) and is constructed “through psychological, cultural, and social means” (West & Zimmerman, 1987, p. 125). Hence, while sex is based on biological factors, gender is socially constructed.

Both West and Zimmerman (1987) and Butler (1999) argue that gender is performative, and is an act of doing rather than an assigned identity set in stone. West and Zimmerman (1987) state that “doing gender” consists “of socially guided perceptual, interactional, and micropolitical activities that cast particular pursuits as expressions of masculine and feminine ‘natures’” (p. 126). The perception of division between men and women being rooted in biology leads to what West and Zimmerman (1987) call role theory. Role theory, also called sex roles or gender roles, attends to the social construction of gender categories. Roles are situated identities, meaning that gender has no specific context, but rather certain roles become gender marked, for example ‘doctor’ and ‘female doctor’. West and Zimmerman (1987) argue that “gender is not a set of traits, nor a variable, nor a role, but the product of social doings of some sort” (p. 129). They claim that a person’s gender is something “that one does, and does recurrently, in interaction with others” (p. 140). Butler (1999), similarly to West and Zimmerman, states that gender is the “repeated stylization of the body, a set of repeated acts within a highly rigid regulatory frame that congeal over time to produce the appearance of substance” (pp. 43-44). Such repeated acts, such as gestures and words, construct the essence of one’s gender. The stylization of the body can further be explored as “the mundane way in which bodily gestures, movements, and styles of various kinds constitute the illusion of an abiding gendered self” (Butler, 1999, p. 179). Butler (1999) maintains that performing gender is done through everyday acts that construct and express an identity, and reasons that gender is not constructed as a stable identity but rather is an identity that changes in time and context and is hence socially temporary.

Furthermore, West and Zimmerman (1987) explore how the distinction between female and male is constructed through ‘doing gender’. Gender differences are done through the “sociocultural shaping of ‘essential female and male natures’” (p. 142), but also involve sex-differentiated factors and functions. For example, the distinction between women’s and men’s bathrooms is based on the functioning of sex-related organs. Moreover, West and Zimmerman differentiate the doing of gender for female and male through the production of behaviour and its gender implications of masculinity and femininity. This distinction between ‘being masculine’ and ‘being feminine’ leads to the construct of gendered stereotypes and preconstructed ideas about what it means to perform femininity, masculinity, and otherness.

Butler (1999) presents that if gender is performative, then there is “no preexisting identity by which an act or attribute might be measured; there would be no true or false, real or distorted acts of gender” (p. 180). Thus, they argue that gender reality is only constructed through sustained social

performances, and that concepts of masculinity and femininity are constituted as part of gender performativity. Butler's (1999) argument that gender is neither true nor false, nor real, is key in understanding how 'genderlessness' can be created in a binary system. Whilst both West and Zimmerman (1987) and Butler (1999) agree that gender is socially constructed, West and Zimmerman (1987) assert that individuals have gender, and gender exists in interactions to establish and communicate the individual's sex category to another person, hence gender existing in a female-male dichotomy. Butler (1999), on the other hand, argues that individuals do gender, and that gender is unstable, fluid, and exists outside of humans. From Butler's (1999) perspective, genderlessness can be understood as a disruption of socially sustained performances that conform to the male-female gender binary, rather than the absence of gender itself.

Lastly, it is valuable to mention that both West and Zimmerman's (1987) and Butler's (1999) are older sources that primarily work with binary understandings of society at that time. However, an overwhelming majority of current gender studies on gender performance dominantly build off these texts, hence why these two sources were used to build a theoretical framework on gender performance over more recent academic works.

2.2 Gender Roles and Stereotypes

Stereotypes play an important role in creating and separating masculinity and femininity in traditional binary structures. By understanding these stereotypes and how gender stereotypes are presented in factors such as fashion and dance, genderlessness becomes more identifiable as it can be separated from the binary expectations upheld by traditional society. In van den Berghe's (2020) analysis on gender roles in advertising for gender neutral fashion, she provides definitions for stereotypes and gender stereotypes. Stereotypes are the beliefs about characteristics and attributes of a social group, and gender stereotypes communicate characteristics and behaviors that are believed to be gender-specific and represent 'masculinity' and/or 'femininity' (Van den Berghe, 2020). Gul-Unlu (2020) further develops the definition of gender stereotypes as "certain behaviours and characteristics, which are expected by the society from women as a group and men as a group" (p. 2). Gul-Unlu (2020) argues that when members in society interact, they identify one's gender over biological traits, physical characteristics, and personality traits. This builds off West and Zimmerman's and Butler's argument over gender being performative, as stylization of the body is used to infer gender. Gender stereotypes are developed due to both biological sex and how the individual performs their gender through physical appearance and behaviour. When there is an absence of information on biological sex, individuals rely on physical characteristics, such as dress, to make gender attributions (Deaux & Lewis, 1984).

2.2.1 Gender Stereotypes in Fashion and Appearance

Dress plays an important role in communicating gender, identity, and constructing stereotypes. Dress, defined by Johnson and Lennon (2015) as the outward arrangement of body modifications and material objects added to the body, is a medium for communication of an individual's ideas about the self (Johnson & Lennon, 2015). Hence, since dress is an outward expression of one's identity, gender is directly correlated with fashion (Hardin, 2024). However, stereotypes and internal biases influence assumptions made about an individual based on how the individual presents themselves through dress, leading to (false or incorrect) assumptions about the individual's gender identity (Hardin, 2024). This is often because "dress is the most visible tool to validate the male/female and masculine/feminine binary" (Reilly & Barry, 2020, p. 11). Reilly and

Barry (2020) however also argue that dress can also be a tool for disrupting and transforming the binary. This disruption can be found in ‘unisex’ fashion, or fashion adapted for both menswear and womenswear, and fashion contributing to ‘gender blurring’, or the rejection of traditional gender roles and stereotypes (Van den Berghe, 2020).

2.2.2 Defining Femininity and Masculinity in Fashion

Dress fashion is most often categorized as feminine, masculine, or a third category with the recent emergence of ‘unisex’ fashion. The two binary categories are at the same time rigid in separating femininity and masculinity from each other, yet also very vague in defining what makes something ‘feminine’ or ‘masculine’. Over time, certain colors, textures, and stylistic choices have been gendered and are stereotypically associated with women or men. For example, the common assumption of the color pink belonging to women and femininity, and the color blue belonging to men and masculinity (Hardin, 2024). Of course, clothing is simply just fabric and has no gender, however, society has fabricated attributions to create fashion that is defined by “codes, seasons, shows, trends and existed under the assumption that gender functions in a binary” (Loureiro, 2023, p. 101).

Within Western cultures, femininity in fashion consists of specific physical attributes and is associated with soft aesthetic choices (Paisley, 2025). The two following fashion blogs present characteristics stereotypically associated with such femininity. This type of source, a blog, is often used by individuals in society to receive advice or inspiration on fashion and stylization, hence influencing common perceptions of what is deemed feminine or masculine. Feminine clothes combine various textures: “Delicate lace, translucent chiffon, and satin offer visual softness while providing elegant movement” and “Soft, flowing fabrics like silk, chiffon, and lightweight wool create an ethereal quality that epitomizes femininity” (Paisley, 2025, ‘Textures and Fabric Selection’ section). Along with flowy fabrics, other textures such as sheer, lace, and tulle fabrics are also associated with feminine style (MYSTYLEBOX, n.d.).

Figure 1 Elements of Feminine Style (Paisley, 2025)

Furthermore, certain silhouettes that accentuate curves or reveal certain areas of skin are also associated with feminine style, such as the ones presented in Figure 1. For example, cropped shirts that reveal the midriff are commonly seen as women’s clothes rather than men’s clothes. The MyStyleBox blog on feminine fashion style also states that pastel tones, embellishments, and

accessories are key elements of feminine fashion. Embellishments include elements such as bows, ruffles, faux fur, lace, and frills, whilst accessories consist of elements such as jewelry, pearls, headbands, stylish glasses, and elegant hats (MYSTYLEBOX, n.d.). Cosmetics and makeup are also traditionally considered feminine.

Masculine fashion style is often seen as the opposite of feminine fashion. In a masculine fashion guide blog, masculine fashion is explained as an approach that focuses on “solid shapes and tailored line” and “different from feminine fashion, which often emphasizes curves, softness, or decorative details” (Ay Pero Que Cute, 2025, ‘What Does “Fashion Masculine” Mean Today?’ section). The blog proposes key traits of current masculine fashion. A first key element is structured shapes, such as boxy jackets, blazers, and trousers. Furthermore, neutral or darker color palettes are more popular, with brighter or bolder colors being rarely used. Another key element, much like in feminine fashion, is texture and fabrics. Fabrics like denim, wool, and cotton that provide strong and sharp lines are associated with a masculine style. Similarly to feminine fashion, certain accessories are also associated with men’s fashion: “Watches, belts, boots, and minimal jewelry are strong choices. A cap, beanie, or clean sneakers can also give your outfit a masculine edge” (Ay Pero Que Cute, 2025, ‘FAQs About Fashion Masculine’ section).

Aside from masculine and feminine fashion, the emergence of ‘other’, or ‘unisex’, fashion style has allowed for an androgynous physical appearance. Androgyny can be defined as “the integration of traditionally feminine and traditionally masculine characteristics within a single individual” (Hoffman, Borders, & Hattie, 2000, p. 476). However, despite the concept of androgyny resisting binary fashion styles, the androgynous style still perceives clothing elements as either feminine or masculine by “taking men’s shapes and adapting them for womenswear, and vice-versa” (Van den Berghe, 2020, p. 21) rather than present complete neutrality from either gender marker. Androgyny must also be differentiated from gender-neutrality, which “can either be achieved by not referring to either sex in any way, or by simultaneously referring to both sexes, without highlighting either one” (Hämäläinen, 2019, p. 7).

2.2.3 Exploring Gender in Dance and Performance

Similarly to fashion, gender can also be performed physically through dance. Similar to clothing, dance is inherently non-gendered, however dance and performance have also been categorized into the binary system. Certain artistic elements in dance, such as different genres of dance or different movements, are categorized as either masculine or feminine.

Feminine styles of dance and movement are classified as “light effort actions (gliding, flicking, floating)” and masculine styles are “strong effort actions (punching, pressing, slashing)” (Midgalek, 2013). Femininity is also associated with greater flexibility, vulnerability such as bent and twisted poses, and gracefulness, whilst masculinity is associated with a stronger and leading tone (Queering DanceSport, n.d.).

It is important to mention that socially constructed ideas on what makes something masculine or feminine are both concrete and vague. To summarize, often stereotypically and in mainstream fashion, femininity in dress and style includes factors like wearing pastel colours, especially pink, wearing noticeable makeup, and wearing certain silhouettes that accentuate female-sex related elements such as the chest or the hips. Masculinity is often the opposite factors, such as wearing no makeup or wearing makeup that is not noticeable, wearing dark or bland colours, and wearing baggy or sharp clothes. The categories of male and masculinity, and female and femininity,

are arbitrary and performative. This means that while these categories are very prominent and impactful in our social lives, justifying why an element is masculine or feminine is ultimately rooted in social conventions rather than inherent characteristics. As West and Zimmerman (1987) and Butler (1999) argue, elements such as dress become gendered through repeated interactions and established social norms, and hence certain elements become commonly associated within one of the male or female socially established categories.

2.3 Gender Beyond the Binary

A multitude of gender identities exist outside of the female-male dichotomy. Identities such as nonbinary, agender, genderfluid, and more have become ways for individuals to identify themselves outside the binary structure (Clupny, 2020). Transgender refers to individuals who do not identify with the gender culturally associated with their sex assigned at birth (Clupny, 2020) and is often used as an umbrella term for identities outside of the binary. Gender identities whose gender is outside the binary conceptualization of gender, such as nonbinary or agender identity, reject “compulsory adherence to the man/woman dichotomy present in Western cultures” (Clupny, 2020, p. 6). Furthermore, these identities are also a form of genderlessness (Clupny, 2020), which is defined as neither male nor female and lacking the elements associated with either gender (Merriam-Webster, n.d.). Kwon (2023) discusses the term genderless in Korean media and how it is used to communicate that a person transcends the boundary between traditional gender expressions, as well as confuses others about the person’s gender.

Identities that fall outside of the man-woman binary structure are often overlooked or erased, such as the USA’s erasure of transgender identities from the Stonewall website. Individuals who identify outside the binary actively take steps in “ungendering their social selves” (Clupny, 2020). In a TED talk, Joel (2022) argues that a world without gender is one where humans with male, female, or intersex genitalia exist, but there are no men and women. This relates to the postgenderism movement that argues that gender is an unnecessary limitation and that the erosion of the gender binary is liberatory (Wikipedia, 2026). Furthermore, this ‘ungendering’ of oneself aligns with ‘gender-free’ expression, where a person is neither male, female, nor any other gender, and in which one’s gender is irrelevant in their life (Wikipedia, 2026). Combining Merriam-Webster’s and Wikipedia’s definitions of genderlessness and gender-free identities, along with Clupny’s ‘ungendering’, these identities involve removing traditional gendered ideas associated with certain elements to redefine these elements to lack gender, rather than creating entirely new non-gendered elements that did not exist before.

2.4 Understanding K-pop

Gender is not performed equally universally; gender is different on an individual, social, cultural, and global levels. Hence, binary performances of femininity and masculinity may differ in different cultures. Therefore, it is important to introduce concepts of masculinity and femininity in Korean music.

K-pop, or Korean popular music, is an aesthetic-driven and stylized genre of music that emerged in popularity from South Korea in the 1950s (The Los Angeles Film School, n.d.). K-pop gained global attention in 2012 due to PSY’s Gangnam Style, and more recently, due to the success of K-pop groups BTS and BLACKPINK (Wen, 2024). Furthermore, these groups appeal to their audience through imagery and aesthetics, and influence fashion trends and youth culture (Wen, 2024). K-pop

has become prominent in the global music industry, and despite its name (-pop), it encompasses various genres of music such as rock and R&B (Wen, 2024).

K-pop is often separated into girl-groups, with female-only members, or boy-groups, with male-only members. Although there are rare instances of co-ed groups, with both male and female members, and solo artists. K-pop groups more often than not adhere to a 'concept'. A concept is the theme of an album or a group's 'comeback', which is when a K-pop artist releases new music after a period of inactivity, usually only a few months, and begins a new era of their music career. This concept influences various factors, such as the songs themselves, the style and dress of the members, the photoshoots and promotional material released to the public, and more (Geddo, 2022). Essentially, the concept forms the image that the group members portray to the public. There is also a 'general' concept, which is an overall theme for the K-pop group's entire career, and is found in all comebacks (Geddo, 2022). Examples of K-pop group concepts include the Girl Crush or Boy Crush concept, which encompasses hard-hitting music, eccentric stylization, and attitude (Geddo, 2022). This concept is very popular, for example global sensations BLACKPINK's debut song "BOOMBAYAH" and BTS's "Danger" both conform to the Girl Crush and Boy Crush concept. The Sexy concept and the Cute concept, which encompass bubbly music and wholesomeness, are also both popular concepts (Geddo, 2022).

2.4.1 Gender and Sexuality in K-pop

Masculinity, femininity, and traditional gender roles in Korea differ from Western standards. Influenced by Confucianism, which emphasizes hierarchical relationships and reinforces patriarchal structures, Korea presents conservative gender roles (Wen, 2024). Wen (2024) presents that misogyny against Korean women, stemming from the belief in Confucianism that "does not regard women as independent individuals, but rather dictates their actions by imposing specific requirements on them" (p. 13), takes form in aesthetic expectations and creates pressure to present an acceptable image. Hence, Wen (2024) argues that this mindset "strengthens the men as subjects, and women are relegated to being the objects of the male gaze's choices" (p. 13). These aesthetic expectations and misogynistic culture have transferred into the K-pop industry: the "over-sexualization and infantilization so as to satisfy men's fantasies, or the reinforcement of the notion that female idols are replaceable and disposable" (Wen, 2024, p. 14). This is important for understanding gender inequality experienced in the K-pop industry and gender performances, especially towards girl-groups who face stricter and conservative gendered expectations. There have also been instances of idols who challenge the misogynistic over-sexualization and infantilization by displaying both femininity and masculinity through confidence and to "inspire their fans to embrace their identity, underlining female empowerment" (Wen, 2024, p. 27).

From a Western perspective, Lee, Lee, and Park (2020) argue that male K-pop artists and boy groups are "redefining masculinity and conventional male beauty standards by diverting from the normative qualities" (p. 5901). Across various K-pop groups, and differing per concept, versatile masculinity is performed: a hybrid form of various masculinities such as beast-like or soft masculinity, which embodies masculine and feminine aesthetics (Lee, Lee, & Park, 2020). This multilayered masculinity challenges hegemonic notions of Western, and white, masculinity whilst also placing K-pop idols as objects of desire of Western fans (Lee, Lee, & Park, 2020). Despite this 'redefining' that Lee, Lee, and Park (2020) identify, boy groups and male K-pop idols remain categorized by the gender binary: they still identify as a boy group and/or a male idol, and are redefining masculinity in popular culture, but are not moving towards genderless identities. Although there have been examples of

Western music artists who have moved beyond traditional binary performance, think of David Bowie and nonbinary singers Demi Lovato and Sam Smith, music in the Western world still mostly conforms to and imposes binary expectations.

Kwon (2023) further expands on the topic of soft masculinity as exhibiting conventional femininity. Kwon (2023) argues that these terms – soft, beast-like, multilayered– used to convey the gender of K-pop idols reproduce binary and cisheteropatriarchal ideas within Korean culture. Despite Lee, Lee, and Park (2020) identifying that boy groups are redefining masculinity in the K-pop scene, Kwon (2023) argues that this redefining, with terms such as ‘soft’ or ‘beast-like’, still genders K-pop idols within a cisheteropatriarchal system. Hence, within the Western context, these idols are indeed challenging traditional expectations of (Western) masculinity, however within the Korean context, these idols still remain inside and reproduce ideas of binary gender expectations imposed by the K-pop industry and Korean culture. However, Kwon (2023) defines the term ‘K(Q)ueerness’ as “as the aesthetics, imaginations, practices, performances, and ideas of K-pop players [...] that have the potential to disrupt the cishetpatriarchal structures of K-pop and create a liberatory space with their unruly, deviant, anti-hegemonic, disturbing, and fluid qualities” (p. 55). Kwon (2023) argues that performances and expressions of gender that are ‘queer’ in contrast to traditional, stereotypical, and normative ideas of gender in Korean culture and music can subvert Korea’s cishetpatriarchal system (Kwon, 2023). Kwon defines this genre of queerness as “an approach, an aesthetic quality, a perspective, a practice, as well as identification and orientation, all of which challenge ‘normalizing mandates’” (p. 54). Kwon’s concept of ‘K(Q)ueerness’ plays a key role in dismantling restricting structures of identity imposed by society.

3. Methodology

3.1 Introducing XLOV

Figure 2 XLOV members (left to right): Wumuti, Haru, Rui, Hyun (XLOV [@xlov_official], 2025f)

XLOV is a four-member group, seen above in Figure 2, that officially debuted on January 7th, 2025, under the company 257 Entertainment, which was recently acquired by WM Entertainment as of March 2026. The oldest member, and leader of XLOV, is Umut Tursun (ئۈمۈت تۇرسۇن), and their stage name is Wumuti. They are ethnically Uyghur, an ethnic group in northwestern China. The second oldest member is Taiwanese member Chen Kuan Jui (陳冠叡). Their stage name is Rui. The second youngest member is Korean member Kim Jin Hyung (김진형). Their stage name is Hyun. The last and youngest member is Kato Haru (加藤 暖琉). From Japan, their stage name is Haru. For this thesis, all members will be referred to by their respective stage names. Figure 2 serves as an introduction to familiarize oneself with the members before observing them in the various settings presented in the data.

The group's name XLOV combines 'X', representing negation and the unknown, and 'LOV', representing incomplete love (iamraeiam, 2025). XLOV is the first K-pop group with a genderless concept: whilst there have been other groups who have presented genderless fashion, XLOV is the first group that presents genderlessness as their central concept (KTimes, 2025). XLOV was formed by the member Wumuti, who is the leader and producer of XLOV, in collaboration with the CEO of 257 Entertainment (원마이크, 2025). Wumuti envisioned a group with XLOV's concept for a long time (원마이크, 2025), and Wumuti hand-picked the members of XLOV: Wumuti, Rui, and Haru were contestants on the survival show *Boys Planet* (2023) together, and Wumuti and Hyun were long-time friends (Arirang Radio K-Pop, 2025).

3.2 Aim and Relevance of Research

Elements such as clothes, makeup, lyrics, and choreography are all inherently non-gendered elements that have become gendered over time and are now key elements in conveying binary gender identities. Since society has created and enforces this binary system of dividing almost everything from clothes to hobbies, to even jobs, into two categories of male and female, concepts

that fall outside of this binary system are often either overlooked or erased. As XLOV performs their concept of genderlessness, they have created a concept that pushes against this binary system that can act as a symbol of resistance in the name of self-expression and identity.

This thesis aims to understand how XLOV constructs genderlessness in a binary society by analysing how XLOV utilizes elements to portray genderlessness. This includes how XLOV themselves understand the concept of 'genderlessness' and how they communicate the meaning of genderlessness through their media. It is important to explore this topic because it actively combats stereotypical and traditional gender expectations and creates visibility surrounding those who identify outside the gender binary.

3.3 Methods and Data

Multimodal discourse analysis is used to analyse how XLOV constructs and portrays their concept of 'genderlessness' in their media representation. Multimodal discourse analysis studies the use of multiple semiotic modes in meaning-making. Semiotic resources, or modes, refer to resources such as language, image, music, gesture, and architecture (O'Halloran, 2021). These resources are systems of meanings, and multimodal discourse analysis is a method that investigates how these modes interact with each other to create meaning-making, or communicate a message (Diggitt Magazine, n.d.). In this thesis, these modes consist of lyrical content, visual aesthetics, choreography, and other symbolic elements, and are analysed to uncover how XLOV combines these elements to create, convey, and perform their message of 'genderlessness'. This is done by identifying gendered codes and their categorization as femininity, masculinity, or ambiguity, followed by examining how these codes are blended or destabilized in order for XLOV to construct genderlessness. The method of multimodal discourse analysis was chosen over other methods of research to be able to identify how the concept of genderlessness presents itself across various modes that can be consumed either individually or collectively (e.g. lyrical content, dance, music video, etc.), and how these modes come together to convey a singular message.

How XLOV constructs and defines their own concept is first explored through various interviews and is analysed via theories on gender portrayal and gender performance. This is analysed first to better understand how XLOV views their own identities and self-articulation of what their concept entails to them, in relation to already defined theories on gender performativity. Building off both XLOV's own definition of genderlessness, combined with the theoretical framework, an analysis is conducted of each of XLOV's title track songs, which are the main promoted songs for an album. XLOV's three title tracks, '*I'mma Be*', '*1&Only*', and '*Rizz*', present three different promotional eras for the group. Using a combination of content to conduct multimodal discourse analysis, the official music video for each song serves as the main focal point. Along with the music videos, each song's 'dance practice' video serves as standalone content to analyse choreography. Behind-the-scenes video for the official music videos allows for analysis of visual aesthetics and other symbolic elements that are key in the music videos. Other social media posts on Instagram are also utilized for a closer look at visual elements such as makeup and outfit details. Lastly, behind-the-scenes for each song recording allows for analysis of the lyrics, any changes applied to the lyrics during recording, and commentary on the lyrics' message.

For each title track, the performance of genderlessness in lyrical content is first analysed. This is then followed by an analysis of choreography, highlighting any moments in the dance practice video that are important in communicating XLOV's concept. Lastly, the music video is analysed, with

a primary focus on dress and stylization of the members and any symbolism presenting ties to XLOV's genderless concept.

Lastly, all findings are discussed to highlight repetitions of patterns and key elements presented in XLOV's media. All findings are interpreted through established theory on gender performativity, construction of femininity and masculinity, and analysed in relation to how XLOV views their own concept.

3.3.1 Data Collection

Data on XLOV's own interpretations of their genderless concept and other gender related topics were collected through two database sources. The first source is a "XLOV Gender Masterlist"¹ document that was uploaded onto the platform X. This fan-made document combines numerous links on conversations between XLOV and fans and/or from interviews and contains various quotes and explanations on both pronouns and gendered terminology regarding XLOV and XLOV's general ideas on gender. This source allows for a full overview of the discussion over XLOV's genderless concept. The second source is also a fan-made project called "XLOVFLIX"², and is a website that contains English translations of XLOV's content in one place: official videos, performances, interviews, livestreams, and more. This website links to either official videos that already provide English subtitle translations, or links to English-translated videos provided by the creators of the website. Hence, any English-translated data content that is not from an official XLOV media page is provided from these two sources. Other sources involve various interview articles and social media posts.

The three title track songs were chosen as the primary focus of this thesis as they provide various settings to explore XLOV's genderless concept. Each music video enables multimodal discourse analysis across multiple elements, such as containing multiple outfits and background settings, and each music video also has additional accompanying media content that is not provided for other XLOV songs. Furthermore, since these three songs are title track songs, they are the most promoted and hence are the contents that are most visible to audiences. Therefore, XLOV's portrayal of their concept is visible and interacted with most often through these three songs and their accompanying media, and therefore have more power in meaning-making and creating an impact.

3.4 Ethical Considerations

It is important to establish that a Western perspective is applied in this research and this thesis takes place within a Western socio-cultural context. Dominantly Western theories and concepts are applied in the analysis, and use Western constructions of masculinity and femininity, which may differ from the Korean construction of the concepts. Western concepts were chosen as XLOV's fans are predominantly an international audience, and XLOV content is often consumed in a Western context and spaces. Acknowledging that this thesis uses a Western perspective, this influences the perception of gender and hence the analysis of how gender, and genderlessness, is performed. Moreover, it is important to mention that the author has followed and actively consumed XLOV's content since October 2025, hence some personal bias may be present. However, the author's experience and attention to XLOV allows for a more personal understanding of the group's concept and content.

¹ <https://t.co/5fgMftsx95>

² <https://xlovflix.carrd.co/>

Furthermore, the data collected for the analysis depends on translated content, either through XLOV's own YouTube English translations, translations provided by Google, or translations provided by XLOV fans across various social media platforms, as explained in the section above. Hence, certain translations may not be fully accurate due to differences in the Korean and English languages. For example, certain phrases or expressions in Korean may not exist in English and are hence translated to the closest meaning. The use of tools in the thesis process is specified in the technology statement in the appendix.

Lastly, it is recommended to watch all three music videos and dance practice videos before proceeding to read the case study.

4. Analysis: K-pop Group XLOV

This case study section begins by introducing and examining how the members define their concept of 'genderlessness' to be able to analyze each title track song alongside XLOV's message. Once XLOV's concept is better understood, each song is individually analyzed, and discussed altogether at the end.

4.1 XLOV and Genderlessness

XLOV has defined their meaning of 'genderlessness' multiple times across various interviews and interactions. To begin, an important distinction is made between XLOV being 'genderless' and performing being 'gender-free'. In an interview with Hellokpop (2025), XLOV said the following:

When we say "genderless," we think it might be a little difficult for English-speaking fans to fully grasp. By "genderless," we aim to break stereotypes that suggest only certain genders can do this or that. The art we express is "gender-free," and we hope it empowers more people to embrace their true selves and pursue who they want to be. (para. 10)

XLOV further elaborates that being genderless is not simply about wearing clothes 'opposite' of one's gender assigned at birth, but rather being able to wear whatever one wants without expectations. Wumuti expresses that the message they want to convey through XLOV is the following:

The message we're aiming to share as XLOV is all about genderless and gender-free concepts. When someone is born, if you're a man and you wear a skirt, that isn't simply being genderless and gender-free. If you were born a woman and wear a suit, that's not genderless and [what] gender-free is. It's about having no standard whatsoever. When you look in the mirror right now, you think "I'd like to wear these clothes" or "this hairstyle and makeup would be nice" or even "I don't need hair and makeup". Without any limitations, the me that you truly embrace is what it is, and what you believe is beauty and what makes something beautiful. We're not focused on who I like or what kind of person I like. We're not having that conversation. It's about what the me I love looks like. It's about "Who is the me that I love?". I think it would be simple if you could see us as a group that sends that message. (한터, 2025)

This message that XLOV presents aligns with Kwon's (2023) discussion over 'K(Q)ueerness' and the term 'genderless' in Korean media. In both quotes, XLOV expresses that they want to break stereotypes and empower people to embrace themselves beyond the gender binary. This depicts how XLOV's message transcends and challenges the cisheteropatriarchal structures that Kwon (2023) explores in Korean culture. XLOV's message coincides with Kwon's concept of 'K(Q)ueerness', as they both emphasize the potential of disrupting traditional gender structures in Korean culture, as well as creating a "liberatory space" (Kwon, 2023, p. 55). XLOV creates a space for individuals to freely express themselves without having to conform to male or female gender codes. Both Kwon (2023) and XLOV use the term 'genderless' as a means of communication to express transcending the boundary of gender expressions and the gender binary. Wumuti further expresses their concept as beyond the gender binary in an interview with MBC Radio (2025):

In society, the clothes we want to wear, our hair, our makeup, nails, the music that we play and how we dance, it is all based on the rigid definition of these two gender options. We don't allow that to confine us. So we just do things with the mindset of how we want to do it, outside of that binary, seeking out all types of things in order to show whatever we want to express, how we want to express it. And the message we want to show to others is that regardless if they're a man or woman, young or old, everyone has a right to discover their own true beauty.

It can be understood that genderlessness, building from West and Zimmerman's (1987) and Butler's (1999) theories on gender performativity, emerges when gender performances do not reproduce social expectations of femininity or masculinity. By rejecting gender codes, or by reworking gendered elements to reject confinement, like Wumuti states, XLOV disrupts traditional binary gender codes by performing gender in ways that do not reproduce female or male binary codes. Instead, XLOV aims to frame themselves and their performances as free from the gender binary and beyond sustained performances of masculinity or femininity.

However, as West and Zimmerman (1987) state that doing gender consists of activities that express masculine and feminine 'natures', West and Zimmerman hence argue that all performances encompass gendered elements leading to assigning gender. Therefore, whilst West and Zimmerman (1987)'s gender theory frames gender as performativity, in the case of XLOV, West and Zimmerman (1987) would argue it wouldn't be possible for XLOV to move outside of the binary, as according to them all activities are tied to either masculine or feminine 'natures'. This is where the research gap on gender-nonconforming identities is prominent, as theories such as West and Zimmerman's that provide a basis for gender studies make it difficult to encompass and involve expressions of gender identity outside the binary. Hence, West and Zimmerman (1987) would argue that what Wumuti describes as 'genderless' is still ingrained in a binary framework. Because of this, it is important to unpack what exactly being 'genderless' encompasses according to XLOV's definition, and to align it with Butler's (1999) theory rather than West and Zimmerman's (1987).

Whilst XLOV's concept is officially being 'genderless', their explanation of their concept is close to what is understood as gender-free expression, in which gender does not define or categorize people's lives and choices (Wikipedia, 2026). As Wumuti states, XLOV does not allow themselves to be tied to either feminine or masculine gender presentation, but rather perform gender as simply being themselves regardless of male or female gender identities. Building off of Butler's (1999) concept of stylization of the body in presenting gender, XLOV presents that they stylize themselves not off masculine or feminine ideals but simply off one's own definition of beauty, supported by what Wumuti stated in the interview quote above. XLOV's stylization is based on individual interpretations of beauty and builds off self-expression rather than socially established gendered codes. Rather than conforming to social constructions of gender, XLOV attempts to individualize their gender expression to each member based on the member's own ideals of how they want to express themselves. It can be seen that each member of XLOV has very individual and distinct stylizations and performances, which will be seen in later sections of this thesis, that create four distinct presentations of gender. In a 2026 interview with iMBC, Hyun clarifies that XLOV does not draw boundaries when it comes to how each member expresses themselves, and that the members maintain different styles from each other. Hyun states that these differences allow them to show something different with each era whilst also highlighting individuality. In the same interview, XLOV constructs their authenticity, stating

that while other K-pop groups embody a concept, XLOV's concept reflects their everyday way of living. The members expressed that their concept feels more natural to them because it was a way of living that they've always experienced and "it's just who I [Wumuti] am" (iMBC, 2026, para. 11). This also differentiates from classic girl groups and boy groups in K-pop who collectively perform femininity or masculinity in a collaborative and uniform way. Furthermore, each member's individuality and variety in gender performance aligns with Butler's (1999) argument that gender is external and fluid. XLOV externally performs genderlessness as a group by not collectively conforming to either male or female conceptions of gender, with each member doing gender differently. Furthermore, by each member doing gender individually and differently from each other, they resist collective gendered norms by rejecting full uniformity within XLOV itself: the members are always stylized differently from each other, which differs from some other K-pop groups where all members wear the same outfits. This also ensures that the members do not collectively perform established gender norms as a group, maintaining their vision of moving beyond gender-binary structures.

It is important to note that while the audience can never be fully certain of an idol's authenticity, here the audience is informed that XLOV does not perform or portray a certain character or persona for their audience. This differs from traditional Korean idols, who may be assigned a role, such as 'the sporty one' or 'the girly one', that they are expected to perform for their audience. At a fan sign event, when a fan asked how Wumuti keeps the image of 'Wumuti' [Umut Tursun], as a person, separate from 'XLOV Wumuti', as an idol, Wumuti stated the following:

For XLOV, from the start, we never tried to fit everyone into one single style. We never had that kind of rule. We're not going to make a concept where anyone has to suppress what they want to do and we're not going to create situations where someone has to pretend to be something they're not. [...] If there's something you [in reference to the other members] want to do, tell me. Just as you are, with your own personality, that's how you should do your activities [referring to events and stage performances]. (Iju 이주 🌻, 2026)

This differs from other K-pop idol groups, where members are assigned personas to play for the audience, even if this persona does not reflect the idol's true character. For example, Jeongyeon from the girl-group Twice was assigned 'the boyish role' in the group and was forced to cut her hair short, making her upset (감별사, 2025). With XLOV, Wumuti states that the personas the audience sees on stage or in interactions reflect the members' true and personal characters, and that XLOV does not force members to adhere to certain stylizations, allowing for the members to set their own boundaries and preferences in performances. Lastly, since XLOV was created and formed by Wumuti themselves, we can assume that there is a level of authenticity due to the members' personal ties to the concept, which differs from other K-pop groups, where members are often scouted for a group. Hence, while Butler (1999) contests the concept of gender authenticity, since gender is constituted through performance, XLOV's performance can be better understood as a reflection of the members' own creative expressions and choices, rather than conforming to a style forced upon them. Therefore, when referring to the member's authenticity throughout this thesis, the term does not refer to the expression of a "true" gendered self. Instead, its significance lies in the members' ability to construct and express their desired identities rather than adhering to a style dictated by industry expectations.

To summarize, XLOV themselves define their concept of being genderless as breaking stereotypes of the female-male binary framework through being able to freely express themselves in terms of gender performance without being confined to a single female or male gender construct. For XLOV, being genderless simply means presenting their true, authentic selves and their understanding of beauty regardless of how society imposes the gender binary. They frame genderlessness as the rejection of gendered expectations. This goes hand-in-hand with Kwon's (2023) discussion on the term 'genderless', as XLOV uses the term to explore beauty and themselves beyond traditional binary expectations of gender identity. Furthermore, XLOV argues that their purpose with their message and concept is to break stereotypes and to convince people to embrace their true selves, aligning with the post-genderism movement that believes that the erosion of binary structures is liberating.

4.2 First Era: 'I'mma Be'

Figure 3 'I'mma Be' Song Promotional Photo (XLOV [@xlov_official], 2024a)

XLOV's debut song *I'mma Be* was first teased in late December 2024 on YouTube and was officially released on January 7th, 2025. With over 6 million views on the music video on YouTube and over 17 million streams on Spotify as of March 2026, XLOV's debut song introduced their concept to the K-pop and global music industry. The song, which mixes English and Korean, is a hip-hop and R&B-based song, with a mysterious atmosphere and intense rebellious declarations of individuality (Reeves, 2025; Lyricsbull, 2025). *I'mma Be* tells a story of escaping oppressive and restrictive structures that limit XLOV's ability to freely be themselves.

4.2.1 'I'mma Be' Lyrics

The debut song's lyrics contain themes of love, resilience, and self-identity. The song begins by reflecting on a reality that seems impossible to escape from, already hinting at the constraints of society's binary gender structures. The song continues by suggesting that societal judgments and barriers must be broken, and one must move with strength and determination. Furthermore, the song suggests that one must find strength in hardship, seen in lyrics such as "I'm walking on the rain/ And I'm dancing on the pain". The post-chorus of the song repeats the phrase "I'mma be your, ooh / ooh, ooh (*I'mma be ya, I'mma be ya*)", expressing commitment to a romantic partner, and this is

expressed neutrally: gendered terms are not used to describe either a female or a male partner. The post-chorus reinforces boldness and confidence in being a transformative presence in someone's life. This theme is seen again in the bridge through the lyrics "Say love me cause you know that i'm the real yeah / 끝나지 않을 love 짚어져가 it's not the end" (English translation: Say love me cause you know that i'm the real yeah / This endless love deepens, it's not the end) (alesaceto, 2025), where love is described as a strong, deep, and endless force in someone's life. Resistance and self-identity are combined to create a message about XLOV's genderless concept. It is explored in lyrics such as "See my body moving like this. I'm riding on the wall of prejudice", in which the body is used as an instrument of resistance to create an undeniable presence, linking the body to going beyond the gender binary. Resistance through the body is also expressed in the lyrics "free the beauty that will unfold on the stage (translated)", depicting that XLOV utilizes their concept of genderlessness to present their true beauty on stage.

XLOV performs genderlessness through *I'mma Be's* lyrics by presenting resistance against conforming to traditional gender roles and gendered Korean standards. Despite having love as a central theme of the song, there are no gendered terms to convey cisheteronormativity, but rather leave love as an ungendered subject. The song conveys confidence in self-identity, presenting the message that XLOV's members will unapologetically be themselves and portray what they believe is beautiful to the music industry. This aligns with the message XLOV aims to convey through their genderless concept, like Wumuti stated: "everyone has a right to discover their own true beauty", regardless of gender roles and conventional beauty standards.

4.2.2 *'I'mma Be' Choreography*

The *I'mma Be* choreography blends both masculine and feminine elements that align with the song's lyrics and message. Movements classified as feminine, defined by Midgalek's (2013) article, are seen mostly through flexibility and delicacy in the *I'mma Be* choreography. For example, seen in Figure 4, Rui displays extreme flexibility, which is often associated with only women being able to do, and Rui follows up this movement with a high kick where their leg goes above their head.

Figure 4 Example of Flexibility in *'I'mma Be' Choreography* (XLOV, 2025b)

Softer, more intricate and delicate movements are seen during the post-chorus, but more masculine choreography is presented both before and after this. For example, seen at 1:32 in the dance practice video, both Hyun and Rui perform hard-hitting, quick, and sharp movements that

convey stereotypical masculine performance. Wumuti at 1:47 performs more soft and elegant movements that are more sensual and fluid, conveying femininity. Hence, rather than performing movements only categorized as masculine or feminine, XLOV blends the two together to create an ambiguous choreography that can be performed by anyone regardless of their gender identity, refusing to reproduce traditional expectations of gender performance in dance.

A key movement in the choreography that symbolizes XLOV's message of wanting to move beyond the gender binary is presented in the first 10 seconds of the choreography, represented in Figure 5. Haru and Hyun sit back-to-back, facing away from each other, representing the gender binary. Wumuti and Rui stand behind them, and both of them reach out to each side, representing that individuals can either follow masculinity, femininity, or follow neither. For a beginning of a choreography of a debut song, this presents to the audience that XLOV is offering the audience a choice to move with them beyond binary structures, and to follow XLOV's message of being your authentic self and present your true beauty, regardless of gender stereotypes and norms.

Figure 5 Beginning Sequence in 'I'mma Be' Choreography (XLOV, 2025b)

4.2.3 'I'mma' Be Music Video

The music video presents various sets. The music video begins by presenting a red exit door, which becomes an important symbol later in the video. The viewer first sees the members in a school room with a chessboard theme: the regular students sit attentively in uniform school outfits, while the members contrastingly sit differently and wear elements that set them apart from the other students. For example, both Wumuti and Haru have diamonds and glittery elements on their faces, and both Hyun and Rui have skirt-like attachments to their school uniforms. Furthermore, Haru wears an argyle top under their blazer, and Rui has their blazer open to reveal a blue dress shirt and no tie. With these two examples, the members of XLOV set themselves apart from both the regular students and from each other.

Figure 6 Example of Differences in Member's Stylization in Comparison to the Regular Students (XLOV, 2025a)

With these scenes, XLOV perform gender outside the binary whilst criticising binary structures. The school set represents how systems impose male-female structures and reject liberty and individuality in gender identity. Seen with the regular students in the music video, boys are expected to wear pants and girls are expected to wear skirts, and both conform to rules imposed on them by 'superior' systems, such as the education system where individuals are expected to adhere to binary structures from a young age. XLOV rejects this conformity of uniform structures within society. They combine both feminine and masculine elements to express their uniqueness from the regular students. For example, Haru wears shorts instead of pants, has a different undershirt, and has makeup with glittery elements which present a gender-blur of both femininity and masculinity. Each member's differences in stylization can be seen above in Figure 6.

The chessboard and chess pieces in the music video represent the strict rules imposed by societal norms on gender identity. In chess, there are set rules that dictate the behaviour of every piece. There is a brief scene where four white queen chess pieces are shown, depicting the four members as powerful pieces yet who stand alone against black chess pieces. One of the queen pieces is knocked over, later depicted as Wumuti in the video, which symbolizes setbacks experienced by those who reject binary structures. This aligns with the erasure and stigmatization experienced by transgender identities outside of the binary structure and depicts the hardships that such identities experience.

The red exit door scenes present an important change in the dress stylization of the members. This stylization is the only moment where the members wear bright colours. Both Haru and Rui have skirt-like elements, a short denim one for Haru and a longer tulle one for Rui. The members, compared to the school uniform outfits, are also more accessorized with a combination of masculine and feminine elements. Supported by Paisley's (2025) fashion blog, XLOV here presents femininity through soft and flowing fabrics, such as Rui's skirt, Hyun's fuzzy gloves, and Haru's loosely knit shirt and fuzzy accessory on top. Wumuti and Rui both also wear tops that are cropped. On the other hand, masculinity is presented through the members' darker fabrics, such as Rui's and Wumuti's mostly black outfits, and all the members wear straight-cut pants that align with a masculine shape. Despite wearing both masculine and feminine elements, these elements balance out and create androgyny. Certain elements, such as denim which is present in both men's and women's fashion, present unisex fashion.

The music video ends with the members walking out of the red exit door, which symbolizes XLOV moving away from the gender binary and refusing to be trapped by socially constructed gender norms. This important ending scene presents again the theme of resistance, the two doors representing an escape from restrictive male/female binary structures.

Overall, with the *I'mma Be* outfits, dress, and stylization here is not used as a tool to validate the masculine-feminine binary (Reilly & Barry, 2020), but rather the variation in masculine, feminine, and unisex elements disrupts socially-constructed gender performances. This rejection of adhering to the female-male dichotomy aligns with gender identities that exist outside of the binary and rejects stereotypical fashion choices that reinforce cisheteronormativity.

4.2.4 Other Elements in 'I'mma Be'

Other symbolic elements are used to portray the concept of genderlessness in *I'mma Be*. The elements of the fox and the siren are used to do so. The song utilizes fox-like elements in the lyrics and in the music video to represent the mythology of the nine-tailed fox, which is a creature that

exists between human and animal and between genders. The nine-tailed fox is a common mythological creature in Chinese, Japanese, and Korean culture (Liao, 2015). The nine-tailed fox occupies a trickster role, and the fox spirit is often seen as cunning and seductive, with the ability to transform or possess young, beautiful women. These fox spirits, although differing in myths per Eastern Asian culture, are associated with “supernatural metamorphic powers and with dangerously seductive women” (Liao, 2015, para. 1).

In the lyrics, the symbolism is seen in the post-chorus, as explained by XLOV in a Hellokpop interview: “ ‘I’mma Be your Woo woo woo.’ It’s reminiscent of a fox’s cry. We think this melody alone expresses the ‘neutrality’ and ‘delicacy’ that XLOV pursues” (iamraeiam, 2025, para. 8). With this fox cry, XLOV portrays a shift in gender expectations and stereotypes, as they transform and transcend the boundary of the gender binary. This lyric also takes a layered meaning that XLOV is the fox and shapeshifter who reveals that the audience’s real desire is to transform themselves and destabilize gender stereotypes. This is further symbolized in the lyrics “I’mma be your wish”. Within the mythology of the nine-tailed fox, the fox reveals that one’s desire was never what they thought it was (Userxlov, 2026). Within this context provided in a fan article, this represents that the audience never wanted a stable gender category, but rather wanted to be like the fox that shapeshifts (Userxlov, 2026). The symbolism of the fox is also seen in the choreography, with XLOV representing themselves as the fox that transcends gender. The choreography presents the symbolism of the fox through the hand gestures, and presents XLOV as seductive and cunning creatures that have the ability to transform and shift the gender binary.

Figure 7 Fox Symbolism in ‘I’mma Be’ Choreography (XLOV, 2025b; XLOV, 2025a)

Another symbolic element is the siren imagery. Seen in the lyrics “사이렌이 울리고 / 소란스럽게”, which has some difficulties being translated into English but roughly translates to “The siren is blaring / Loudly” (alesaceto, 2025; Slay(슬레이) et. al, n.d.), the song utilizes this element to create a sense of urgency that demands people to evacuate, in this case evacuate from binary gender structures. This element of time running out is also seen in the music video, in a very quick scene of an analog clock ticking and through the choreography where the members represent this clock, with a ticking sound present in the song. This symbolizes XLOV’s time as part of the gender binary structure has run out, as they move beyond these structures.

Figure 8 Clock Ticking Symbolism in 'I'mma Be' Choreography (XLOV, 2025b)

To summarize, XLOV introduced their concept of genderlessness through their debut song by combining symbolism and imagery in their lyrics, choreography, and music video to support their concept's message. This is mainly seen in the symbolism of the chess pieces and the nine-tailed fox, directly depicting how XLOV rejects gender binary structures.

4.3 Second Era: '1&Only'

Figure 9 '1&Only' Song Promotional Photo (XLOV [@xlov_official], 2025c)

XLOV's first comeback song, *1&Only*, was released on June 13, 2025, and is XLOV's most popular song so far. The music video has over 23 million views on YouTube and 66 million streams on Spotify. The song has a laidback, groovy, and rhythmic tempo that is inspired by Afrobeat and Afro

pop, and contains lyrics in Korean, English, and a bit of Spanish. The song sends a bold message about confidence, passion, and love. The title track song encompasses what the album *I ONE* is about, as Hyun explains:

The meaning of 'I ONE' is, first, that I am the only one, so it's like I'm just one person, there is no other. It means "*I am one. I am a unique existence.*" Then, the other meaning of 'I ONE' is somewhat similar to the sound of "I want," which also contains the meaning of "I want it." (Sayson, 2025).

XLOV's *I ONE* album focuses on expressing uniqueness, individuality, and empowerment, encouraging the audience to do the same. This correlates to the broader message XLOV expresses through their genderless concept, encouraging the audience to express their true selves and to perform gender based on individual choices rather than conforming to constrictive gender structures and stereotypical binary roles. Essentially, *I ONE* encourages the audience to focus on what they want in terms of identity and self-expression.

4.3.1 '1&Only' Lyrics

Unlike *I'mma Be*, the song *1&Only* doesn't directly address XLOV's genderless concept but rather performs genderlessness through the song's theme. The song presents the message of passion and love that is shared with another person. The song is, in a sense, flirty and inviting, and like *I'mma Be*, excludes any signs of gendered language to convey this message. Here, XLOV again portrays the theme of love as non-gendered and rejects cisheteronormativity. The only key example where XLOV directly addresses gender in this song is through Wumuti's lyrics "Call me Papi Chulo, Mamacita". With just this simple phrase, XLOV is performing genderfluidity. They convey that all gendered terms can be used to address them, allowing them to transcend binary boundaries as they shift both within and beyond gender binary structures. Despite these lyrics conveying a traditional and binary form of gender (Papi Chulo = male, Mamacita = female), genderfluidity participates in transgender identities, as it rejects sole male or female binaries, and these lyrics depict XLOV as fluid within binary structures. Furthermore, these lyrics depict Kwon's (2023) discussion on transcending traditional gender expressions and confusing others about a person's gender as this switching between gender terms does not produce concrete binary gender identities for the members.

4.3.2 '1&Only' Choreography

Figure 10 Example of Flexibility in '1&Only' Choreography (XLOV, 2025d)

Similar to *I'mma Be*, the choreography for *1&Only* combines both masculine and feminine elements to disrupt traditional gender expectations in dance. Explored in the '*Gender in Dance and Performance*' section, dance movements are often categorized as feminine or masculine through associations of elements such as flexibility, grace, and strength. In *1&Only*, femininity is performed through actions like flexibility, exemplified in Figure 10, and attention to delicate details, seen at moments like 0:21-0:29 in the dance practice video. The choreography also involves movements such as twerking, which is stereotypically associated with women's dance. XLOV incorporates these feminine elements with masculine, hard-hitting dance. For example, the dance segment 0:45-0:54 and Haru's solo choreography at 2:16 exemplify traditional expectations of male dance by performing strong gestures and sharpness. These elements combined create a gender hybridity that allows XLOV to perform genderlessness.

Rather than reproducing stable performances of gender, XLOV blends socially constructed gendered dance to create a hybrid performance that aligns with XLOV's message of being able to freely express themselves without constraints of the binary gender construct. Also seen in *I'mma Be*, this hybridity in choreography, which reflects Butler's (1999) argument that gender is constructed through repeated bodily actions and stylization, challenges conventional gendered expectations by displaying that dance can be performed by any body and is not tied to any specific gender. It also rejects performing strictly masculine or feminine expectations of K-pop performances. Furthermore, from West and Zimmerman's (1987) perspective, choreography is a social performance in which gender is communicated. In this case, *1&Only* presents a dance style that disrupts binary assumptions in dance, allowing for XLOV to communicate genderlessness to the viewing audience.

4.3.3 '*1&Only*' Music Video

Figure 11 "Sick of the Same Crap?" Sign at Beginning of Music Video (XLOV, 2025c)

The members of XLOV have confirmed that the music video storyline is a sequel to the storyline of *I'mma Be* (Arirang Radio K-Pop, 2025). The members have exited the cage, being trapped in the game of chess that represents binary structures, and enter a new world where they can be themselves. The music video begins with the members coming across a sign that says "sick of the same crap? Its your choice, leave them behind, get your freedom back". This message directly addresses the audience, presenting them with the choice to leave behind the restrictive structures of

gender binary norms and expectations, and for the audience to gain their freedom by being able to be their true, authentic selves with no restrictions. This is a recurring theme in XLOV's music, where they invite their audience to become part of the collective in freely expressing identity beyond the gender binary.

In a majority of the music video, we see the members enjoying themselves, having fun, and presenting their energetic choreography. This sends the message that being free from restrictive gender structures leads to happiness, and encourages the viewer to join XLOV in performing genderlessness. This continuation of the storyline of rejecting socially constructed gender roles and expectations aligns with the framework of Butler (1999) on sustained performance for communicating gender, as this repeated performance of genderless behaviour presents XLOV's message and doesn't reproduce socially-constructed performances of binary gender.

While the storyline portrays the freedom of binary structures, XLOV mostly performs genderlessness through their outfits. As established, dress and stylization are main modes of communicating gender identity, and play a role in reinforcing stereotypes associated with binary structures. The full white outfits at the beginning of the music video interrupt binary readability. The members all wear chunky platformed and heeled shoes that are extensively decorated, wear accessorized press-on nails, and all have flowy or lacey elements incorporated into the outfit. Seen in Figure 9, Rui wears a lacey wrap-like skirt over pants with a lace top and has long hair, and Wumuti wears a floral-like headpiece with a lace-like top and has glittery elements across their face, all elements associated with feminine fashion. Hyun wears a sheer top and has decorative accessories around their waist, and Haru has a plainer white ruffled-layered top with a fuzzy accessory around their waist. These lightly-coloured outfits are highly accessorized with delicate details that portray socially constructed ideals of femininity. This 'gender blending' in fashion, which Van den Berghe (2020) describes as the rejection of traditional gender roles, of feminine-coded details with items associated with masculine fashion, such as structured and straight shapes, disrupts the distinction between masculine and feminine fashion codes. Since, according to Deaux and Lewis (1984), dress is used by others to identify and assign gender, this disruption of gendered fashion expectations destabilizes this visual marker used to assign gender, making binary gender less visible among the members.

Despite these outfits blending both masculine and feminine elements, the feminine elements are much more visible compared to the feminine elements presented in *I'mma Be*, leading to these elements standing out and presenting the outfits as more feminine-coded. Essentially, whilst it is still visually difficult to assign a binary gender, these white outfits read mostly as feminine-coded mixed with masculine elements because these outfits present new elements, such as the ones in Figure 12, XLOV have not previously been shown in *I'mma Be*.

Figure 12 Example of Member's Accessory Stylization from Behind-the-scenes Video (XLOV, 2025f)

XLOV presents a duality against these feminine-coded outfits with their next outfits in the music video. These outfits mostly contain muted tones with a pop of colour and portray fashion aligned with masculine expectations. Despite these outfits being more masculine, XLOV gender-blurs them with feminine elements, such as Haru and Hyun wearing cropped shirts, Rui wearing a tulle skirt, and Wumuti having fur on the shoulders of their top, all elements described by the two feminine fashion blogs. This duality is presented again in the last outfits seen in the music video: the outfits themselves are masculine-coded but are blended with feminine details. For example, Wumuti has a short tulle skirt and Rui has longer hair. XLOV utilizes traditionally gendered clothes and combines them in ways that resist clear gender categorization.

This blending of stereotypically masculine and feminine fashion demonstrates how XLOV rejects binary structures as they refuse to adhere to a gendered expectation. Rather than reproducing stable performances of either binary gender, XLOV combines and performs elements that align with both binary categories which challenges binary expectations and stereotypes. This aligns with Wumuti’s message of their genderless concept: XLOV is rejecting the binary and stylizing themselves in the way they want to. Despite the group presenting very stylized outfits that combine both feminine and masculine elements that produce a collective image, for example the all-white outfits presenting uniformity, each member is still able to express their own individuality in each outfit. This individuality of each member is visible as certain members repeatedly wear certain elements, such as Rui with tulle skirts which are presented twice in *1&Only* and once in *I’mma Be* as seen in Figure 13. Another example of how the members individually express themselves is through their nails. For example, Hyun and Haru are seen mostly wearing shorter nails, perhaps associated with more masculine expectations, while Rui and Wumuti tend to wear longer, more feminine-coded nails. Haru is seen wearing long shorts, occasionally with a skirt, while the other members wear long pants, also occasionally with skirt-like elements. These small yet significant details allow the XLOV members to present elements that are unique to their individual identity, whilst also collectively performing gender-free stylization. This further displays how they convey authenticity; the members can express their individual stylistic choices even in situations where they are collectively dressed in a certain theme, such as all white outfits, and even the all black outfits also seen in the music video.

Figure 13 Rui’s Repetition of Tulle Skirt (XLOV [@XLOV_official], 2024b; XLOV [@xlov_official], 2025d; XLOV, 2025e)

Certain dress elements, such as cropped shirts and skirt-like elements, transferred from *I’mma Be* in *1&Only*, however XLOV performs genderlessness slightly differently in *1&Only* than in *I’mma Be*. Whilst both songs utilize blending feminine and masculine coded elements in order to

make gender attributions difficult, *1&Only* presents a different form of hybridity. *I'mma Be* presented balanced hybridity with equally mixed masculine and feminine coded outfits, creating more androgynous dress stylization. On the other hand, *1&Only* presents feminine-coded outfits with masculine elements, such as the white outfits discussed, and masculine-coded outfits with feminine elements, such as the second outfits discussed. In a sense, this instability in dress performance across the two songs further solidifies the performance of genderlessness itself. As West and Zimmerman (1987) and Butler (1999) argue gender is a sustained performance, XLOV's performance of genderlessness itself is not sustained, as it performed slightly differently each time, thereby reinforcing Butler's (1999) notion that gender is not a fixed identity, but is rather fluid and ever-changing. Despite gender through dress being performed each time differently, the outfits homogenously perform the same message that XLOV aims to convey.

4.4 Third Era: 'Rizz'

Figure 14 'Rizz' Song Promotional Photo (XLOV [@xlov_official], 2025g)

XLOV's second comeback with their first mini album UXLXVE released the title track *Rizz* on November 5th, 2026. With over 9 million views on YouTube and over 15 million streams on Spotify, *Rizz* is XLOV's second most viewed music video to date. With a trap-pop and R&B sound, the song makes a bold statement about confidence, lust, and attraction.

4.4.1 'Rizz' Lyrics

Rizz differs from *I'mma Be* and *1&Only*, as it makes selective decisions about a gendered word. A notable example is the lyrics "Take it slow, boy, I'm gonna kill it hard, like, yeah". On its own, the term 'boy' doesn't inherently disrupt heteronormativity, however as XLOV don't position themselves within conventional binary categories, the object of attraction in the song is not clearly situated in a heterosexual framework. In such a sultry song about attraction, these lyrics leave space for interpretations and avoid positioning the theme of attraction within a fixed gender binary. This ambiguity aligns with Kwon's (2023) 'K(q)ueerness' where instances like this help dismantle traditional and restrictive structures on identity by refusing to align with a clear gender category. Furthermore, the lyrics don't enforce any sexual meaning, but are rather phrased as an act of confidence and dominance over the other person ("boy"). These lyrics emphasize the speaker, in this case Hyun, as confident and assertive regardless of their gender identity, which destabilizes conservative ideas on who is allowed to express such agency in romantic interactions.

Furthermore, through the *Rizz* behind-the-scenes recording, we learn that another gendered term was removed from the song (XLOV, 2025j). The lyrics "How you stop the game?" were originally "Lucky, lucky girl" in the demo version of *Rizz*, which is heard at 4:22 in the behind-the-scenes video. This shows that XLOV are very selective of when they use gendered terms, and of the message and effect of using such gendered terms presents. Whilst lyrics like "Lucky, Lucky girl" could reinforce sexualization and objectification of women by presenting them as "lucky", lyrics such as "Take it slow, boy" challenges the other person ("boy") in terms of attraction and confidence. The removal of the lyrics "Lucky, lucky girl", which inherently comes off as more sexual than "Take it slow, boy, I'm gonna kill it hard, like, yeah", removes the positioning of women as objects of the male gaze, which is a dominant idea in Korean culture. By choosing the lyrics "How you stop the game?" over "Lucky, lucky girl", XLOV decides to remove gender entirely. When XLOV decides to have gendered terms in their lyrics, they choose to do so in a way that challenges traditional and conservative norms. Whilst this does not directly relate to XLOV's performance of genderlessness, it relates to the broader message of breaking out of stereotypes in Korean culture.

Similar to *1&Only*, *Rizz* presents the themes of attraction and confidence as genderless, pushing the message that these themes are achievable to individuals regardless of gender identity. This aligns with XLOV's general message that everyone deserves to be able to freely express their own true beauty, regardless of social binary structures.

4.4.2 'Rizz' Choreography

Figure 15 Example of Flexibility in 'Rizz' Choreography (XLOV, 2025j)

Rizz, similarly to *I'mma Be* and *1&Only*, performs traditionally feminine and masculine elements of dance. XLOV again utilizes flexibility to perform femininity, seen at the beginning of the choreography where all members perform the splits, an element traditionally associated with female dance. Other feminine elements are seen at moments such as 1:13-1:20 and 1:41-1:47 in the dance practice video, where the members perform sensual, almost provocative, movements that align with the song's message about confidence and attraction. This is also exemplified at 1:31, where two members crawl through the other two members' legs and interact at the end in an alluring way. Traditional expectations of masculine dance are performed at moments such as 1:36-1:40 and during the chorus part of the song, where the members perform stronger movements that assert dominance. Aside from these explicit moments, in which either feminine or masculine dance is dominant, the rest of the *Rizz* choreography homogenizes the dance styles, making it difficult to categorize the movements as either feminine or masculine. This effectively performs genderlessness as neither femininity nor masculinity is sustainably performed, hence disrupting binary expectations of choreography. The way in which XLOV performs genderlessness in *Rizz* is very similar to the way it is performed in *I'mma Be* and *1&Only*, where the combination of gender-coded movements destabilizes the visual clarity of gendered performances, and hence doesn't reinforce binary distinctions for the choreography as a whole.

4.4.3 'Rizz' Music Video

The opening scene of *Rizz* presents the same world as *1&Only*, and assumes that the events in the *Rizz* music video take place after the events of *1&Only*. As the song begins, the viewer sees the members for the first time. In this scene, the members present two sets of outfits already. The first outfits, the ones seen in Figure 14, combine dark, tan, and neutral colours with each member wearing similar items. Each member wears long press-on nails, a top that exposes the midriff, boots, jean pants with the exception of Haru who wears jean shorts, and each member has some type of hair accessory and a faux fur accessory. Rui wears a long blue-greyish wig, Wumuti has long red dyed hair, Haru has their hair spiked up, and Hyun wears a long hat-like accessory. These outfits present unity whilst also presenting each member's own stylistic choice. Similarly to the outfits in previous music videos, XLOV prevents fixed gender attribution to perform genderlessness. This is further exemplified in the second outfits, which are briefly seen at the beginning of the music video but mostly towards the end, where the members wear black sharp blazers, dark jeans, and men's dress shoes. This stylization alone reproduces stereotypical expectations of masculinity. However, XLOV combines this with feminine accessories, as seen in Figure 16. The blazers combine tulle and lace fabrics with glittery and intricate designs, each in the member's own respective representative colour. Both Hyun and Rui's blazers are longer in the sides and back, but are shorter in the front to expose the midriff and have mainly tulle fabric sewn onto them. On the other hand, Wumuti and Haru have shorter cropped blazers, with a black undershirt, and have mainly lace and ornamental designs. The members also all wear white wigs, with Hyun and Haru having shorter, more masculine presenting hairstyles, and Rui and Wumuti having longer, more feminine presenting hairstyles.

These outfits exemplify how XLOV present unstable conformity to the gender binary, effectively performing genderlessness as a group whilst also allowing each member's dress stylization to have unique elements to each member. It is important to mention that whilst elements such as Hyun and Haru having shorter hair and Rui and Wumuti wearing longer hair may portray Hyun and Haru as more masculine than Rui and Wumuti within the gender binary, XLOV's message is to portray

that clothes, and in the broader sense stylization, are genderless and that the members wear what makes them comfortable and makes them feel beautiful. Building off XLOV's message, Hyun and Haru are not more masculine, or less feminine, than Rui and Wumuti, but rather all members exist on the same level where variations in masculinity and femininity don't create a difference in identity. Instead, the members function as equally valid forms of expression within the same genderless framework.

Figure 16 Second Outfits Worn in the 'Rizz' Music Video (XLOV [@xlov_official], 2025h)

The third outfits seen in the music video are darker in colour, with more stereotypical masculine silhouettes that utilize feminine accessories to create an outfit that goes beyond gender binary expectations. This involves again utilizing elements such as skirts, cropped or tight tops, long hair extensions or wigs, and wearing press-on nails. Lastly, the members all wear visible makeup. Whilst in other music videos the members wore more natural-looking makeup or had glittery elements glued to their faces, *Rizz* presents all the members wearing heavier makeup, communicating a feminine aspect to their stylization that is bolder than in previous eras.

These outfits perform genderlessness in the same way that is performed in *1&Only*, as they utilize a hybridity of masculine and feminine elements to disrupt gender attributions and present uniqueness and individuality. This performance in *Rizz* is accentuated by the background characters, who are dressed in torn, black clothes, with their hoods drawn up and with black paint covering the top half of their faces. By not wearing the same outfits as these hooded figures, XLOV's members stand out in their unique attire. This illustrates how XLOV stands apart from the gender binary. They refuse to blend into social expectations of gendered identity, and instead choose to dress themselves as they please and express their uniqueness and individuality. While it initially appears that XLOV performs androgyny, the exaggerated contrast in feminine and masculine elements combined with the lack of stable gender references, no gender performance is sustained, hence creating genderlessness.

Aside from XLOV performing genderlessness through dress, some elements in the music video also present XLOV's concept. This is seen in scenes such as the one in Figure 17, where Rui is bending backwards, almost in an attempt to move out of reach of the hooded figures, with the text

“Don’t Cross the Line” as Rui and the hooded figures stand inside a chalk circle that is present throughout most of the music video. In a later scene, we see Haru run outside this line and away from the hooded figures, and then all four members running around outside the chalk circle. This chalk circle represents society’s binary expectations of gender performance, which restrict individuals from exploring beyond this binary. Hence, the text “Don’t Cross the Line” represents society discouraging individuals from performing gender outside the male-female binary, and encouraging conformity to traditional and stereotypical societal expectations.

Figure 17 Rizz 'Don't Cross the Line' Scene (XLOV, 2025h)

XLOV presents that individuals do not have to conform to these social expectations, and can have the opportunity to turn away from it, or run away from it, as Haru does in the music video. The scene with all four members running outside this circle presents that XLOV rejects this binary gender structure and will refuse to conform to it. Throughout the music video, the members are seen interacting both inside and outside this chalk circle. This suggests that XLOV utilizes these structures to perform genderlessness. As XLOV defines genderlessness as allowing people to be themselves and find their own true beauty, XLOV presents that individuals can transform and bend binary structures to help an individual perform what they define as beauty. For example, XLOV play with binary structures to perform beauty and perform their own individuality: they use stereotypes such as feminine hairstyles, makeup, nails, and masculine colours, clothes, and also again hairstyles, to be able to freely express themselves. They play within binary structures. However, they also move beyond these structures by rejecting them. Rather than simply merging masculinity and femininity and presenting Hämäläinen’s concept of androgynous stylization as they did in *I'mma Be*, XLOV’s stylization destabilizes the audience’s ability to assign gender. Since, as Deaux and Lewis (1984) argue, individuals rely on characteristics such as dress and physical appearance to make gender attributions, XLOV effectively performs genderlessness as these gender references are absent. This furthermore also disrupts gender binary structures, as these gender references are used to reinforce gendered expectations and stereotypes. Hence, within the *Rizz* music video, genderlessness is

performed both through dress stylization and through visual elements in the video that directly address stepping outside of gender binary structures.

5. Discussion

XLOV presents very similar portrayals of genderlessness across the three eras. In all three title tracks, they utilize a hybridity of traditionally masculine or feminine elements in dress stylization. Despite stereotypically masculine and feminine dress elements being visually present, elements such as certain fabrics or silhouettes discussed in the fashion blogs in section 2.2.2, XLOV stylize themselves in a way that makes it difficult to attribute a binary gender to the members. Hence, in all three eras, XLOV portrays dress stylization that doesn't validate the male – female binary, and rejects traditional gender roles by dressing in a way that doesn't reproduce strictly masculine or feminine traditional stereotypes or expected gender roles. XLOV also portrays genderlessness the same way in all three choreographies for the three songs. Each choreography has an element that displays extreme flexibility, along with delicate and graceful elements that convey femininity, combined with masculine-coded elements such as hard-hitting moves that convey dominance and a stronger presence. The music videos similarly contain visual elements that directly address or criticise the gender binary. This is seen in the chessboard and red doors in *I'mma Be*, the "sick of the same crap?" poster in *1&Only*, and the chalk circle in *Rizz*.

There are some differences in genderlessness portrayal in the title tracks, notably between *I'mma Be* and the two following title tracks. Whilst XLOV performs genderlessness through more androgynous clothing in *I'mma Be*, both *1&Only* and *Rizz* present more theatrical and dominating division between masculine and feminine elements: certain feminine elements such as heavier makeup, longer nails, and wigs are more noticeable. Despite these differences in dress stylization, all three songs convey the main message XLOV aims to send on being free from binary structures and displaying their true, authentic selves.

Furthermore, differences in stylization between the members themselves are noticeable and distinct from one another. As a part of XLOV's message with genderlessness is to stylize themselves according to each's own idea of what beauty is, each member presents different and distinctive elements that convey individuality. For example, Rui's repetition of feminine elements such as displays of flexibility and wearing a tulle skirt and Haru's preference for shorts whilst the other members wear pants, seen in Figure 18, depicts that while XLOV maintain a collective image for their genderless concept, their stylization allows for the members to perform according to preference rather than conforming to uniform group stylization that often occurs in K-pop performances.

Figure 18 Example of Repetition in Haru's Dress Stylization (XLOV, 2025a; XLOV [@xlov_official], 2025e; XLOV [@xlov_official], 2025d; XLOV, 2025g)

Aside from rejecting traditional gender roles and stereotypes within gender binary structures seen mostly in Western society, XLOV also rejects traditional Korean expectations. They do so by performing feminine characteristics that do not over-sexualize or infantilize the feminine image, and by performing masculinity in a way that does not reproduce cisheteropatriarchal ideas that Kwon (2023) explores. In doing so, XLOV also performs Kwon's (2023) concept of 'K(Q)ueerness', which also disrupts binary structures in the K-pop industry. XLOV presents their concept as an intervention against restrictive structures, and encourages their audience to pursue authenticity in gender identity rather than conforming to binary expectations.

The analysis of XLOV's portrayal of genderlessness gives insight into how conventional gender binary elements themselves can be utilized to reject and create resistance to restrictive gender structures. This rejection of the male – female gender dichotomy, which aligns with gender identities outside of the gender binary as well as the post-genderism movement, furthermore brings attention to gender identities that are censored, erased, or ignored in Western popular culture discourse. Lastly, the analysis across the three eras allows for beginning to bridge the research gap on genderlessness portrayal in popular culture and media, as the analysis provides insight into a multitude of stylization factors, such as dance, dress, and other visual elements.

6. Conclusion

This thesis aimed to examine how XLOV performs genderlessness across their three title track songs, based on how XLOV challenges traditional gendered expectations in order to answer the following research question: “How does K-pop group XLOV construct and portray the concept of ‘genderlessness’ in their title track songs ‘*I’mma Be*’, ‘*1&Only*’, and ‘*Rizz*’?”. The analysis demonstrates that XLOV’s performance of genderlessness is not done through the absence of gendered elements, but rather through fluid gendered performance. Using multimodal discourse analysis across lyrical content, choreography, and dress, the findings present that gendered elements that align with stereotypical expectations of femininity and masculinity are performed but are not sustained in order to produce an un-gendered identity.

Building off West and Zimmerman’s (1987) and Butler’s (1999) theories on gender being a socially sustained performance dependent on “repeated stylization of the body” (Butler, 1999, p. 43), XLOV rejects society’s binary frame by not conforming to sustained gendered expectations of the stylization of either femininity or masculinity. As XLOV refuse to “do” gender in a maintained manner that conforms to conventional gender expectations, they destabilize binary structures. Through stylization, XLOV transcends the boundary between traditional gender expressions by not reproducing sustained characteristics that lead to the audience not to be able to make gender attributions. They also perform genderlessness by performing themes such as romance and attraction without conforming to cis-heteronormative expectations by generally excluding gendered terms, making the lyrical message and choreography accessible to all individuals regardless of gender identity.

It is valuable to note that while XLOV disrupts conventional binary gender norms, they utilize recognizable masculine and feminine codes, and their performance of genderlessness depends on binary characteristics. Whilst this visibility of gendered elements raises questions on whether XLOV’s performances can be considered truly “genderless” in the sense of the absolute absence of gender, their performance aligns with XLOV’s own definition of their genderless concept. Through interviews and extra content, XLOV defines their concept as being able to freely express themselves beyond binary structures, and being able to freely express their true beauty. Due to the current lack of academic studies on genderlessness as a concept, it is most commonly understood as the absence of gender (gender-less). However, this case study on XLOV demonstrates the relevance of studying gender-nonconforming identities to be able to more accurately redefine the concept of genderlessness to be more encompassing and inclusive in understanding various forms of gender expression.

XLOV utilizes gendered elements to create moments of contradiction, making it difficult for the audience to attribute gender categorization despite the undeniable presence of stereotypically feminine and masculine characteristics. XLOV’s performance of genderlessness destabilizes binary gender structures through the use and disruption of its own roles and stereotypes. This is seen across the three title tracks analysed, but is done so differently. In *I’mma Be*, genderlessness is communicated as a form of resistance and is mainly done so through symbolization and visual elements. Destabilization of binary structures is performed differently in *1&Only*, where XLOV presents multiple aestheticized gendered expressions within the same space. This evolves in *Rizz*, where it is utilized as a source of confidence and aims to redefine gender norms. This variation across the three music videos depicts that XLOV’s genderless concept is not static, but rather shifts according to context, message, and XLOV’s own personal preferences in stylization.

Possible future research on this topic involves audience reception of XLOV and their message, analysis, and comparison between XLOV and other Western or Korean artists who are also gender-nonconforming, and further analysis of XLOV's whole discography and their evolution in genderlessness portrayal. Analysing audience reception would help gain further insight into the influence K-pop idols have on fandom spaces, consumer practices, and Korean music discourse. Furthermore, as XLOV is the first K-pop group with the concept of genderlessness, comparing audience reception to XLOV compared to other K-pop girl groups or boy groups could bring insight into how media consumers and fans respond to gender-nonconforming and queer identities and differences in idol perception. Audience reception to XLOV could also help better understand LGBTQ+ safe spaces that fans create with each other and the impact of having these safe spaces and XLOV media representation on mental health. Comparing XLOV's gender expressions to those of other Western or Korean artists who are also gender-nonconforming would allow to explore how gender expressions differ in media. As XLOV is a group that has brought a new concept to media, comparing them to other artists would highlight what elements have already been seen by other artists and what new elements XLOV has brought to the stage. Additionally, analysing XLOV's whole discography and their portrayal of genderlessness would help further develop what has been stated in this thesis, and would help further expand on reconstructing the definition of genderlessness. Analysing the whole discography would also explore how XLOV portrays genderlessness in other music genres. Both songs *1&Only* and *Rizz* are classified as (K-)pop songs, and *I'mma Be* as (K-)R&B, making this thesis' analysis limited to two genres of music. Further analysis would explore other genres of music, such as XLOV's song *BIZNESS* which is (K-)hip-hop, and *Kiss and say goodbye* which is a (K-)ballad song. Lastly, further analysing other portrayals of gender non-conforming identities in media could benefit in developing better understandings of the spectrum of gender identities present in society, how genderlessness presents itself in other aspects of society, and how genderlessness fits in as a gender category in gender studies. Overall, as XLOV has brought a new concept and performance of gender identity to the global music scene and is relatively early in their career, XLOV presents itself as a new source for a case study in gender and media research.

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8. Appendix

8.1 Technology Statement

This thesis was written and edited in Microsoft Word. Microsoft Word's built-in spelling and grammar checker was used in the writing and editing process of this thesis. Following using Microsoft Word's spelling and grammar checker, the tool Grammarly was used as a secondary spelling checker.

Grammarly was strictly used to correct any spelling mistakes. Grammarly was not used to generate or re-phrase any text. No tools or services were used to paraphrase text from other sources. No tools or services were used to typeset or generate any text. No generative AI or any other AI tool was used during the entire thesis process. All text written in this thesis is my own, aside from quotes that are properly cited.

This thesis is entirely my own and was written by me. All sources are properly cited and can be found in the reference list.